

PARTICIPATION OF POLITICAL PARTIES IN THE ELECTORAL PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN

Qarshiyev Nurmuhammad Olimjonovich

NUUZ: Acting Associate Professor of the Department of "Political Science".

E-mail: nurmuxammad.qarshiev@mail.ru

Tel: 90 975 90 70

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14922640>

Abstract

The acceleration of political processes in the world also accelerates democratic changes within the political system. The interdependence of the party system and the electoral system and their complementary concepts are relevant to their study as an object of research.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has adopted several regulatory legal acts aimed at simplifying the participation of political parties in electoral processes. Furthermore, to enhance the involvement of political parties in elections and increase their influence in society, a "mixed electoral" system has been introduced. This electoral system was implemented for the first time in the context of Uzbekistan and proved to be successful.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, political party, electoral system, majoritarian, proportional, mixed electoral system, democratic elections, parliament, Legislative Chamber, electorate.

Introduction. The influence of the institution of a political party on the democratization of elections in the world is increasing. Political parties are political structures that ensure the diversity of opinions and ideologies in the country and demonstrate the will of voters in governance. Political parties are usually a link between the state institution and the people, as well as an institution that carries, creates, and promotes an ideology. When it comes to the electoral process and the participation of political parties, According to Article 64 of the "Election Code" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Nomination of candidates for the Presidency of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be carried out by the higher bodies of political parties[2]. That is, according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the right to nominate candidates in elections is granted only to political parties.

Also, to ensure equal participation of political parties in election processes, they will be given equal opportunities in terms of propaganda and financial support. According to Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Political Parties," "The state guarantees the protection of the rights and

legitimate interests of political parties, creates equal legal opportunities for them to fulfill their statutory goals and objectives.

State bodies of power and administration, enterprises, institutions, organizations, and their officials are prohibited from interfering in the internal affairs of political parties or obstructing their activities in any way if their activities are carried out by the law and their charters.

It is established that political parties are not allowed to interfere in the activities of state bodies and officials[3].

Main Part. In Uzbekistan, legislation on the "Electoral System" and the activities of "Political Parties" is considered one of the leading countries among the states of Central Asia in terms of its compliance with democratic principles. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also contains articles on the activities of the "Electoral System" and "Political Parties." Chapter XXII of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is called the "Electoral System," and Article 128 of it states: "Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall have the right to elect and be elected to the representative bodies of state authority. Every elector shall have one vote. The right to vote, equality, and freedom of expression of will shall be guaranteed by law"[1].

Also, democratic electoral processes are being carried out in the country based on the "Electoral Code" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in 2019. This code fully complies with international electoral standards. For example, Article 3. "Basic principles of conducting elections in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Elections in the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be held based on universal, equal, direct suffrage by secret ballot.

Elections shall be held openly and transparently[2].

The principles and norms of international law serve as the basis for democratic elections. The main documents reflecting international electoral standards are:

- Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN General Assembly, December 10, 1948).
- European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (1950).
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (UN, 16 December 1966).

These documents state that the principles of universal, equal, direct, and secret voting are fundamental characteristics of basic democratic elections.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has also aimed to further democratize the electoral process, simplify the participation of political parties in it, and most importantly, create convenience for voters, and shape state governance through fair and transparent elections. We can observe that the level of voter participation in electoral processes, political activity, political participation, political awareness, and political culture is growing year by year.

According to the results of the 2024 elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils held in Uzbekistan on October 27, the total number of voters in the country by election day was 19 million 944 thousand 859 people. The number of voters who participated in the elections was 74.72 percent, or 15 million 27 thousand 529 people, compared to the total number of voters. For comparison, in the 2021 elections to the State Duma of Russia, voter turnout was 51.72 percent [6]. In the 2023 parliamentary elections in Kazakhstan, one of the leading countries in the Central Asian region, 6.5 million voters out of a total of 12 million voters participated. 54.21 percent of the total number of voters participated in the vote, with the lowest figure recorded in Almaty (25.82) [5]. Based on the above, we can say that Uzbekistan is one of the leading countries in the region in terms of public participation in political processes, particularly elections.

In the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils held in Uzbekistan on October 27, 2024, according to the general results of the elections for the Legislative Chamber, the Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, which is considered to be a supporter of a free economy and a reduction in the state's share in the economy, belongs to the liberal-democratic movement in its ideological orientation, the main part of its electorate is made up of the middle-class property owners, representatives of the middle class relying on liberal ideology, entrepreneurs and enterprising farmers, and has a center-right position in the spectrum - the movement of entrepreneurs and businessmen - won 64 deputy seats.

The Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "Milliy Tiklanish" (National Revival), which is considered to be a supporter of economic freedom while preserving national values, belongs to the conservatism trend in its ideological orientation, and its main electorate is composed of intellectuals, representatives of science, education, culture, art and information, youth, scientists, teachers, educators, creative people, athletes, representatives of tourism, folk medicine, and community workers, and is located on the right side of the spectrum. It won 29 deputy seats.

The Ecological Party of Uzbekistan, which is considered to be a supporter of strengthening state control over environmental protection, accelerating the transition to a "green economy", and creating a favorable environment for the population, whose ideological orientation belongs to the ecologist movement, the main part of its electorate is made up of employees of environmental protection organizations, citizens who are not indifferent to environmental protection, and whose position in the spectrum is left-center, won a total of 16 deputy seats.

The People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, which is considered to be a supporter of expanding the state's participation in the economy and a socially oriented economy, belongs to the social democratic trend in its ideological orientation, and its electorate is mainly composed of people in need of social protection, representatives of social sector organizations and budget organizations, pensioners, the disabled, single elderly people, women with many children, and orphans. It occupies a left position in the spectrum, occupying a total of 20 deputy seats.

The Social Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "Adolat", which is considered to be a supporter of maintaining state participation in recognizing economic freedom and social equality, belongs to the social democratic trend in its ideological orientation, and its electorate consists mainly of highly qualified specialists, budget employees, teachers, doctors, engineers, technicians, scientists, and representatives of the service sector, and its position on the spectrum is close to the center-left, won 21 [4] deputy seats.

The above figures show that, accordingly, supporters of ideas based on liberal-democratic ideology constitute the majority among the population, followed by conservatism, social democracy, and environmentalism. In Uzbekistan, open. Democratic electoral processes are taking place based on mutual, healthy competition between political parties. The participation of the media in the elections is becoming more active, they are actively covering the processes and organizing various television debates.

Conclusion. In ensuring the development of a free civil society based on democracy, the issues of political parties and their open and transparent participation in electoral processes are of great importance. The conduct of elections based on democratic principles depends on political parties. Also, for political parties to properly shape state governance, fair and transparent democratic elections are necessary, first of all. It follows that the open and

competitive participation of political parties in fair and transparent electoral processes is one of the main conditions for democracy.

References:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. [Matn] Rasmiy nashr. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston” nashriyoti, 2023. – 80 b. ISBN 978-9943-9506-0-3.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Сайлов кодекси.26.06.2019.<https://lex.uz/docs/4386848>
3. “Сиёсий партиялар тўғрисида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонуни. <https://www.lex.uz/acts/54191>
4. Сайлов натижалари эълон қилинди. https://uza.uz/uz/posts/saylov-natizhalari-elon-qilindi_650961
5. Ионова.Е. Парламентские выборы в Казахстане – 2023. Центральная Азия в глобальном мире. https://www.imemo.ru/files/File/magazines/rossia_i_novay/2023_02/15-Ionova.pdf
6. Итого выборов в Государственную Думу VIII созыва. <http://duma.gov.ru/news/52313/>

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES

